

Effect of submergence for 7 and 10 d on plant height, flowering duration, and varietal recovery. Pulla, Andhra Pradesh, India, 1984 kharif.

Growth stage	MTU4870 (MTU4569/ARC6650)		MTU5182 (MTU4569/ARC6650)		MTU5293 (MTU4569/ARC6650)		NC92 (pureline selection)		FPAR7360 (Patnai 23/IR8)	
	7d	10 d	7d	10 d	7d	10 d	7d	10d	7d	10d
<i>Plant ht (cm) at maturity</i>										
Active tillering	102	93	95	85	93	85	137	126	90	82
Maximum tillering	77	—	86	95	—	—	117	94	80	81
Panicle initiation	—	—	64	—	—	—	88	—	—	—
Booting	45	—	50	—	—	—	66	57	54	—
Control	112		109		106		156		101	
<i>Flowering duration (d)</i>										
Active tillering	139	146	139	143	151	152	141	141	141	146
Maximum tillering	151	—	151	153	—	—	142	144	147	152
Panicle initiation	—	—	154	—	—	—	150	—	—	—
Booting	157	—	157	—	—	—	155	160	155	—
Control	157		157		—		155		155	
<i>Recovery (%)</i>										
Active tillering	100	100	80	40	80	20	100	20	80	20
Maximum tillering	80	0	40	20	0	0	100	60	80	40
Panicle initiation	80	0	20	0	0	0	40	0	0	0
Booting	60	0	60	0	0	0	100	60	60	0

Plant height was reduced (12-54%) and flowering duration increased (5-19%) with submergence. These effects

were more severe under 10 d submergence.

Recovery was highest in MTU4870

at active tillering stage; NC492 exhibited good recovery at all stages. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Varieties screened for acid-saline soils

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Soil salinity is also associated with soil acidity in the coastal area of West Bengal. A pot culture experiment screened eight rice varieties on an acid soil. Seedlings were transplanted in pots containing 8 kg of soil (pH 3.5, ECe 4.5 dSjm). N was added at 60 kg/ha. Each variety was replicated three times.

Khao Dawk Mali and RD19 from Thailand and Mahsuri seem promising

(see table). Sterility in Khao Dawk Mali was minimal. Length of panicle and grain weight were higher in Khao Dawk Mali. From those agronomic

characteristics, Khao Dawk Mali and RD19 may be considered for coastal acid-saline soils. □

Variety performance in acid saline soils in West Bengal, India.

Variety	Av ht (cm)	Tillers with panicles (no./pot)	Grain (g/pot)	Straw (g/pot)	Sterility (%)	Length of panicle (cm)	Duration (d)
Khao Dawk Mali	112.3	6.0	12.6	38.9	28.6	24.0	130
Lemo	109.3	15.3	2.3	62.1	81.1	21.6	162
Mahsuri	131.0	10.0	9.0	52.4	38.0	19.7	130
IR26	76.7	10.7	6.5	19.0	79.5	18.5	111
Kajalsali	99.0	7.0	0.3	18.6	83.9	16.0	125
RD19	75.7	7.3	15.1	28.7	49.6	17.0	152
SR26B	107.7	3.0	3.6	14.7	62.4	20.3	152
Pokkali	79.7	10.3	3.7	12.0	50.8	15.5	111
CD (5%)	13.9	5.9	3.7	18.7	3.0	1.1	